

PREVENTION OF KIDNEY DISEASE AMONG THE ELDERLY

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Abstract:

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is increasing rapidly worldwide and is projected to be the fifth leading cause of life lost worldwide. One of the main causes of health care costs is the accident of SBK. Dialysis and transplant costs account for up to 3 percent of the annual health budget in high-income countries.

Keywords: *Chronic kidney disease (CKD), kidney dysfunction, kidney failure disease (CKD), diabetes mellitus (DM), cardiovascular disease (CKD).*

Introduction

Among the factors that contribute to the emergence of the disease, attention is growing, in some cases, lifestyle and environmental characteristics that are common to many of these diseases, including contributing to their development mechanisms. Nephrological aspects of this common problem are particularly evident in its interdisciplinary nature. [2.5] The concept of chronic kidney disease (CKD), its main purpose is, on the one hand, the phenomenon and slowing down of the development of kidney diseases of various etiologies early and as a result, however, delaying the development of chronic kidney failure with subsequent replacement kidney therapy, on the other hand, the risk of cardiovascular complications decreases, occurs as a result of impaired kidney function. [9.18] The CBK concept also makes it more realistic. new preventive work of the doctor in this direction. On World Kidney Day 2020, the company emphasizes the importance of preventive measures - be it primary, secondary or tertiary. [17.20]

Primary prevention of kidney disease should focus on modifying risk factors and addressing structural abnormalities of the kidneys and urinary tract, as well as exposure to environmental risk factors and nephrotoxins.

Introduction: At the threshold of the 20th and 21st centuries, the world community faced not only a medical but also a global problem. A pandemic of chronic non-communicable diseases is of social, but also of great socio-economic importance. [2] It kills millions of people every year,

causing severe complications related to disability and necessity. Among them, kidney diseases have a high prevalence among the population. It leads to a decrease in the quality of life, high patient mortality and the need to use expensive methods. [11.17]

Replacement therapy in the terminal stage - dialysis and kidney transplantation. At the same time, the development of medical science and pharmacology at the end of the 20th century laid the foundation for the development of new medicine. [8] Highly effective and inexpensive preventive methods that significantly slow the progression of chronic kidney disease, reduce the risk of complications and the costs of treatment. These situations require the adoption of a new strategy for defining and stratifying health systems. Severity of chronic kidney disease. There is a need to develop simple criteria and universal. Classifications, therapeutic effects, and a universally accepted interpretation of the severity of kidney damage are also needed to assess the degree of renal dysfunction, prognosis and accurate planning. [13.19] Solving medical, social and medical-economic problems. Only on the basis of comprehensive approaches and uniform terminology, it is possible to adequately assess the level of disease and prevalence, compile regional and national data. National registries of patients with impaired renal function and, based on this, the calculation of the relevant need, current treatment methods, as well as the necessary financial costs should be planned.[21]

Currently, about 850 million people suffer from various kidney diseases. One in ten adults worldwide suffers from chronic kidney disease (CKD), which is always irreversible and mostly progressive. The global burden of SBK is increasing, and by 2040, SBK is projected to be the 5th most common worldwide. are the most common causes of years of life lost worldwide. SBK progresses to end-stage renal disease (ESRD), in which life cannot be saved without dialysis therapy or transplantation.[15.18]

SBK is a major cause of catastrophic health care costs. Costs for dialysis and transplantation are 2–3% of the annual health budget in high-income countries; these countries spend less than 0.03% of their total population. Importantly, kidney disease is preventable and progression to end-stage kidney disease can be delayed with basic diagnosis and early treatment, including appropriate lifestyle changes and dietary interventions.[12] According to definitions by experts, including the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, the term "prevention" generally refers to activities classified under the following three definitions:

Primary prevention includes: Intervening before health consequences occur to prevent disease onset or injury before the disease process begins,

Secondary prevention includes: Preventive measures to prevent the development of more serious problems, leading to early diagnosis and timely treatment of the disease, and screening to detect diseases in their early stages;

Tertiary prevention refers to managing the disease after it is well established to control the progression of the disease and the development of more severe complications, which is often done. targeted interventions such as pharmacotherapy, rehabilitation, screening and treatment of complications. To achieve effective primary prevention, interventions should focus on the two main risk factors for CVD, including diabetes and hypertension. [22]

The main pathophysiology of the rapid development of chronic kidney disease, as in resistant hypertension, is associated with permanent damage to the kidney structure and nephron loss, and is associated with increased interstitial fibrosis. In patients with acute SBK, uremia and related anemia, mineral and bone diseases, cardiovascular Treatment of diseases such as vascular disease is of great importance for these patients to continue to live as long as possible. [1]

Conclusion: Given the urgent need to increase education and awareness of the importance of preventive measures, we propose the following:

Promotion of healthy diet, healthy lifestyle, development of national projects to prevent disease.

It is necessary to inform the population about kidney diseases, to explain their causes. With the help of roundtable discussions and medical information leaflets

Development of national projects to raise awareness of kidney disease prevention and strengthening in primary care.

Develop population-based approaches to manage the major known risk factors for kidney disease, such as hypertension, diabetes, and obesity.

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